

A novel proxy for tracking the provenance of dust based on paired E_1' -peroxy paramagnetic defect centres in fine-grained quartz

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Key Points

- New sediment provenance tool exploits E_1' and peroxy paramagnetic defects in quartz
- New proxy successfully differentiates quartz in loess from two different basins in Central Asia
- Potential applications for identifying climate-driven source change through time in loess and other sedimentary sequences

Abstract

Crystal lattice defects in quartz have long been exploited for age determination, yet also show potential for sediment provenance studies. Here we introduce a novel method for tracking aeolian dust provenance by utilising the natural accumulation of E_1' and peroxy defect centres in quartz. Our approach is based on the previously observed premise that E_1' and peroxy centres arise from Frenkel defect pairs, and that their concentration increases with age of the quartz-bearing source rock. We propose that these defect centres can be utilised as a characteristic feature of the source rock and consequently, for fingerprinting sediments derived from it. We successfully apply our new protocol to distinguish fine-grained quartz extracted from loess deposits from two regions in Central Asia which are known to derive

37 from different source material of differing age. Our method offers strong potential for
38 identifying variability in source, both spatially and through time down sedimentary
39 sequences.

40

41 **Plain Language Summary**

42 Identifying the origins of dust deposits allows us to reconstruct sediment transport pathways
43 which are essential for understanding past atmospheric circulation patterns. Here we propose
44 to exploit the characteristics of two naturally occurring defect centres in crystalline quartz,
45 the E_1' and peroxy centres, as a means to distinguish sediment deriving from different
46 origins. These centres occur as pairs and are hypothesised to increase with the age of the
47 quartz-bearing rock. By this logic, the E_1' and peroxy centres can be used to determine the
48 lithic origins of sedimentary quartz in a similar way to detrital zircon-based provenance
49 techniques, while analysing a more ubiquitous mineral (quartz). We apply our approach,
50 which uses a simplified protocol for measurement in contrast to earlier studies, to
51 successfully distinguish between loess (wind-blown dust deposits) from two different basins
52 in Central Asia. Our new method holds great potential in its application to loess sequences as
53 well as other sedimentary archives.

54 **Keywords:** Provenance, Quartz, Defect centres, Loess, Electron Spin Resonance

55

56 **1. Introduction**

57 Identifying the original source rocks of sediments is important for understanding sediment
58 cycling. For aeolian sediments, pinpointing provenance has additional advantages of
59 facilitating the reconstruction of transport pathways that relate to atmospheric circulation, and
60 thereby changes in climate dynamics through time. Aeolian loess deposits have long been
61 recognised as valuable archives of past climates in terrestrial environments (Kukla, 1988;
62 Schaetzl et al., 2018). Loess sequences represent long-term accumulation of aeolian dust and
63 thus identifying their provenance provides an important proxy for reconstructing changes in
64 atmospheric circulation through time. A number of established tools are used to identify the
65 source of dust in loess deposits. These include grain-size analysis, in particular grain sorting
66 and end-member modelling, to elucidate transport modes and likely source area types

67 (Vandenberghe, 2013; Li et al., 2018); major and trace elemental composition of bulk dust
68 (Sun et al., 2002; Újvári et al., 2008); radiogenic isotope signatures (Sr and Nd) characteristic
69 of clay minerals (Chen et al., 2007; Rao et al., 2015; Ben-Israel et al., 2015); and detrital
70 zircon age profiles (Pullen et al., 2011). Whilst these methods are widely used to identify
71 relative changes in dust sources through time, they rely either on materials found in very low
72 concentrations (e.g. detrital zircons) or aggregated bulk measurements from multiple size
73 fractions which are likely to have been transported from both distal and proximal sources
74 (e.g. major and trace elements, radiogenic isotopes). Furthermore, post-depositional
75 weathering can alter *in situ* chemical signatures within loess, rendering certain analytical
76 techniques, if uncorrected, inaccurate for provenance (Yang et al., 2001).

77 Given the limitations of the above-mentioned provenance techniques, there has been
78 increasing interest in the characteristics of mineral quartz as a tool for linking dust sources
79 and sinks. There are obvious advantages in using quartz as a provenance tool: not only is it
80 ubiquitous, but also highly resistant to weathering and diagenesis (Goldich, 1938). A number
81 of quartz-specific petrographic, isotopic and geochemical provenance methods have been
82 proposed (Bernet & Basset, 2005; Nagashima et al., 2007, 2017; Shimada et al., 2013,
83 Ackerson et al., 2015). Of these, electron spin resonance (ESR) signal of various defect
84 centres in quartz has been increasingly applied to fingerprint sources in sedimentary settings
85 (Nagashima et al., 2007, 2011; Tissoux et al., 2015; Wei et al., 2020).

86 ESR measures the intensity of paramagnetic species (containing an unpaired electron) in a
87 material. Lattice defects and impurities in quartz give rise to various paramagnetic defect
88 centres. E_1' is one such centre (Weil, 1984), comprising an unpaired electron in an oxygen
89 vacancy ($\equiv Si\cdot$, Fiegl et al., 1974) that are known to arise from diamagnetic oxygen vacancies
90 ($Si=Si$, Jani et al., 1983). The most commonly used ESR based provenance protocol utilises
91 the heat treated- E_1' (hereafter referred to as HT- E_1') intensity of quartz by measuring the
92 intensity of the E_1' centre following gamma (γ) irradiation and thermal treatment (Toyoda &
93 Hattori, 2000; Toyoda et al., 2016). It is based on the premise that γ -irradiation and
94 subsequent heating facilitate conversion of quartz diamagnetic oxygen vacancies into
95 paramagnetic E_1' centres resolvable by ESR and expressed as HT- E_1' . The HT- E_1' intensity
96 has been observed to increase with rock age (Toyoda et al., 1992) and is assumed to reflect
97 the total number of oxygen vacancies, which is characteristic of the rock type and

98 consequently of the source rock from which the quartz is derived (Toyoda & Hattori, 2000;
99 Toyoda et al., 2016). The HT-E₁' intensity is utilised in combination with the crystallinity
100 index of quartz as a common provenance tool (Nagashima et al, 2007, 2011; Toyoda et al.,
101 2016), since the combination of these is interpreted to reflect the age, formation and
102 crystallisation conditions of quartz in the source rock.

103 Here we investigate a simplified new provenance method based solely on the analysis of two
104 naturally occurring paramagnetic defect centres in quartz, the E₁' and peroxy centres, using
105 ESR. The formation and characteristics of E₁' and peroxy centres in natural and artificial
106 quartz have long been the subject of empirical study (Weeks, 1956; McMorris, 1970;
107 Stapelbroek et al., 1979; Friebele et al., 1979). Odom and Rink (1989), however, were the
108 first to observe that E₁' and peroxy signals in quartz increase with the age of granitic host
109 rocks, and are positively correlated. Following which, Rink and Odom (1991) proposed that
110 these defect centres arise from Frenkel defect pairs formed by alpha-recoil nuclei, emitted by
111 alpha-emitting elements (U and Th) and accumulated in rocks through time. If this principle
112 holds true for all rock types and the mechanisms for defect formation are understood, then the
113 E₁' and peroxy signals have obvious applications not only as geochronometers (Odom &
114 Rink, 1989) but also for sediment provenance. In this study, we investigate and apply this
115 new method to distinguish quartz in loess sediments from inland Asia. Additionally, we
116 compare the natural E₁' with HT-E₁' characteristics to elucidate differences between our new
117 method and the previous approach (Toyoda and Hattori, 2000).

118 Inland Asia represents one of the world's major atmospheric dust source, both past and
119 present (Kok et al., 2021), and has been the regional focus for investigations using ESR
120 signals of quartz as a provenance technique (Sun et al., 2007, 2008). The basins to the north,
121 east and west of the Asian high mountains (the Pamirs, Alai-Altai and Tien Shan) lie in
122 topographic rain shadows and represent substantial sinks for glacially- and fluvially-derived
123 sediment from the uplands (Schaetzl et al., 2018; Figure 1). In particular, the loess deposits of
124 arid Central Asia (ACA) and the Chinese Loess Plateau (CLP) reach hundreds of metres in
125 thickness (Liu, 1985; Li et al., 2015) representing long-term substantial accumulation, and by
126 extension, likely distal sources of global aeolian dust. Distinguishing between various
127 potential dust sources in inland Asia is important at multiple scales. At regional levels,
128 identifying changes in source down loess sequences enables reconstruction of variability in

129 dust transport pathways and atmospheric circulation through time. At global scales, it can
130 help identify the relative contributions of different basins to the generic “Asian” mineral dust
131 identified in Greenland ice cores (Svensson et al., 2000; Bory et al., 2003) and Pacific Ocean
132 marine sediments (Nakai et al., 1993; Letelier et al., 2019).

133

134

135 **Figure 1.** Regional setting and location of the loess sites under study. The elevation map was
136 created using SRTM (Shuttle Radar Topography Mission) data provided by AW3D of the
137 Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency.

138

139 In this study, we characterise the natural E_1' and peroxy centre intensities of loess from two
140 basins in ACA, the Ili basin and Tajik depression of southeast (SE) Kazakhstan and
141 Tajikistan respectively (Figure 1). Recent studies based on geochemical fingerprinting and
142 back trajectory analysis indicate that these two loess regions derive sediment from different
143 source areas (Li et al., 2018; Li et al., 2019; Fitzsimmons et al., 2020). The potential
144 significance of the region for global atmospheric dust loads past and present, coupled with
145 the likely discrete sources for the two basins, make them well suited for targeted spatial and
146 temporal comparison of quartz characteristics for provenance using our new method.

147

148 **2. Material and Methods**

149 We undertook measurements on fine-grained (4–11 μm) quartz extracted from loess samples
150 collected from five loess sections in Central Asia (Figure 1 and Figure S1). Four of these
151 sections, Panfilov (PAN), Ashubulak (ASH), Taukaraturyuk (TAU) and Malubai (MAL), are
152 located along a c. 200 km east-west transect of the Zalisky-Alatau range in the Ili basin of SE
153 Kazakhstan. The fifth site, Karamaidan (KAR), is a c. 60 m-thick partial section of a c. 130
154 m-thick loess-paleosol sequence, located in the foothills of the Gissar mountain range on the
155 northern margins of the Tajik Depression, in southern Tajikistan (Figure 1). We analysed 114
156 samples; 59 from SE Kazakhstan and 55 from Tajikistan. A detailed account of sampling, site
157 description and age-range, sample preparation, instrumentation and measurement protocols
158 are provided in the Supporting Information (SI).

159 We performed two sets of experiments on fine-grained quartz:

160 (i) To test our new approach, we measured the intensity of E_1' and peroxy centres for all
161 samples. These measurements were conducted on natural quartz samples as is, without
162 any prior treatment and we hereafter refer to these measurements as the natural E_1' and
163 peroxy intensity.

164 (ii) To understand differences between our new approach and the previous ESR-based
165 provenance method, we measured the HT- E_1' intensity following published protocols
166 (Toyoda & Hattori, 2000; Nagashima et al., 2007) and compared them to the natural E_1'
167 intensity for all our samples. This involved irradiating all the samples with a γ -dose of
168 2000 Gy, followed by heating them to 350 °C for 15 minutes to obtain the HT- E_1'
169 intensity. Further, we test our approach and evaluate the need for γ -irradiation and
170 thermal treatment prior to E_1' measurement, by investigating the variation of ESR
171 centres (E_1' , peroxy and Al-hole) with γ -irradiation (varying from 0 to 40000 Gy) and
172 temperature (300, 350 and 400 °C) for two representative samples, one from Kazakhstan
173 (A0016, TAU) and the other from Tajikistan (A0329, KAR). Detailed descriptions of
174 experimental parameters are given in the SI.

175

176 **3. Results and Discussion**

177 **3.1. Paired E_1' -peroxy centres in quartz: Methodological considerations linking quartz**
178 **crystal defect dynamics to provenance**

179 Our measurements of the natural E_1' and peroxy intensities of 114 Kazakh and Tajik samples
180 indicate that the natural intensity of E_1' and peroxy centres yield a positive correlation, with a
181 Pearson coefficient of 0.72 (Figure 2a). This supports the hypothesis that these ESR centres
182 indeed arise from Frenkel defect pairs in quartz as per Odom and Rink (1989), and justifies
183 our exploration of both the natural E_1' and peroxy signals for their application as indicators of
184 provenance.

185

186

187 **Figure 2. (a)** Cross-plot of natural E_1' and peroxy centre intensities of fine-grained quartz
188 from Kazakhstan and Tajikistan based on our new approach; **(b)** Comparison between natural
189 and heat-treated (HT) E_1' and peroxy intensities.

190

191 Although intuitive, the measurement of ‘natural’ signals for provenance remains largely
192 unexplored. Our provenance approach, based on natural E_1' and peroxy signals, represents a
193 simpler protocol than the hitherto established method based on HT- E_1' intensity (Toyoda et
194 al., 2016, and references therein). Figure 2b compares the natural E_1' and HT- E_1' results for
195 all samples. We observe that γ -irradiation and heating simply increases the signal intensity
196 beyond the natural E_1' in all samples. This indicates that the natural E_1' intensity produces the
197 same inherited provenance characteristics as HT- E_1' intensity, and implies that γ -irradiation
198 and heating may not be necessary for our samples.

199 The proposed mechanism for formation of the HT-E₁' in the established provenance
200 protocols (Toyoda & Ikeya, 1991; Toyoda & Hattori, 2000) suggests that γ -irradiation creates
201 hole-supplying Al-hole centres (which arise from Al impurities in quartz), and post-
202 irradiation heating causes the migration of holes from the Al-hole centres. The released holes
203 recombine with one of the two electrons of the diamagnetic oxygen vacancies, giving rise to
204 an oxygen vacancy with an unpaired electron, i.e. an E₁' centre. Therefore, γ -irradiation and
205 thermal treatment essentially converts all diamagnetic oxygen vacancies - which are
206 characteristic of a given rock - into E₁' centres, known as HT-E₁' centres (Toyoda et al.,
207 2016, and references therein). Meanwhile our results on natural E₁' measurements suggest
208 that sample pre-treatment by γ -irradiation and heating is unnecessary for ESR-based quartz
209 provenance methods. Therefore, we undertook an additional series of irradiation and heating
210 experiments on two representative samples, A0016 (Kazakhstan) and A0329 (Tajikistan), to
211 systematically assess the effects of γ -irradiation and thermal treatment on ESR centres (E₁',
212 peroxy, Al-hole centre), and whether such pre-treatment is necessary for ESR-based
213 provenance studies.

214 First, we tested the effect of γ -irradiation on the ESR intensity of natural E₁', peroxy and Al-
215 hole centres. We irradiated 11 aliquots of each sample with a γ -dose varying from 0 to 40000
216 Gy and measured the intensity of each centre. We observe that, overall, the natural E₁'
217 intensity does not change with γ -irradiation (Figure 3a). Our observations corroborate with
218 results obtained from fine-grained quartz from other regions (eastern Europe and North
219 America; Figure S2). Likewise, the natural intensity of the peroxy centre for both samples
220 does not vary with γ -dose (Figure S3). We note that the uncertainty for repeat measurements
221 on the same aliquot for peroxy signal (Figure S3) is 10-20% higher than for the natural E₁',
222 which has an uncertainty of <1%. This is most likely due to the weak peroxy signal observed
223 in our samples. By contrast, the natural Al-hole centre intensity increases exponentially with
224 increasing γ -dose (Figure S4).

225

226 **Figure 3.** Variation in natural E_1' and HT- E_1' (350 °C for 15 min) intensity of fine-grained
 227 quartz (a) with γ -dose for sample (i) A0016 and (ii) A0329. The inset in each plot shows the
 228 variation over the lower dose range (0-2000 Gy) for the respective sample; (b) with depth (or
 229 increasing absorbed dose) at site KAR.

230

231 Second, we tested the effect of temperature on irradiated quartz E_1' and peroxy centres for
 232 the same two representative samples (A0016 and A0329). All γ -irradiated aliquots (n=11) of
 233 each sample were heated to 300, 350 and 400 °C for 15 min, followed by measurement of the
 234 resulting E_1' and peroxy centre intensities. In both samples, E_1' intensity increases with

235 temperature, peaks at 350 °C, and thereafter decreases (Figure S5a, b). The E_1' intensity at
236 any given temperature does not change with increasing γ -dose (Figure S5c, d), which can also
237 be seen in the constant ratio of HT- E_1' to natural E_1' intensity for both samples (Figure 3a).
238 In contrast, the peroxy signal shows minimal change in average intensity with increased
239 temperature (Figure S6). However, the generally weak peroxy signals produce high scatter in
240 the data, rendering assessment of peroxy intensity response to increasing temperature
241 difficult.

242 Our experiments on fine-grained quartz have two important implications for measuring
243 natural E_1' as a provenance signal. First, E_1' and HT- E_1' intensity remains unchanged with
244 increasing γ -dose, and the ratio between the two signals remains constant (Figure 3a). This
245 suggests that heating increases net E_1' intensity, and irradiation has no effect. This is the case
246 not only for our samples from two regions in Central Asia, but also for detrital quartz from
247 modern river sediments (Wei et al., 2017). We conclude that natural E_1' reflects the quartz
248 characteristics just as well as the HT- E_1' signal and argue that γ -irradiation and heating is not
249 necessary. Second, in both our samples, the intensity of the Al-hole centre increases with
250 increasing γ -dose, in contrast to natural E_1' and HT- E_1' . If we assume the proposed formation
251 mechanism of HT- E_1' centre to be true (Toyoda & Ikeya, 1991; Toyoda & Hattori, 2000), our
252 observations imply that the number of diamagnetic oxygen vacancies in our samples is less
253 than the number of holes released from Al-centres upon heating, even for unirradiated
254 samples. This further sustains our view that the γ -irradiation step is redundant for our
255 samples.

256 Our work is based on the premise that naturally occurring E_1' and peroxy centres accumulate
257 in rocks over million-year time scales, primarily due to the effect of heavy particle irradiation
258 and thereby show an increase with rock age (Odom and Rink, 1989). Therefore, the use of
259 these defect centres as provenance indicators relies on the fact that their intensity does not
260 change significantly with ionising radiation received during transport and/ or burial as a result
261 of the short time spent by quartz in sedimentary settings as compared to that in the source
262 rock. A recent study by Toyoda and Amimoto (2021) suggests that apart from ionising
263 radiation received in rocks, exposure to radiation during its sedimentary history is also likely
264 to alter the E_1' signature of quartz. We, therefore provide further evidence that the E_1' signal
265 is independent of ionising radiation received during transport and/ or burial by examining the

266 natural E_1' and HT- E_1' intensity variation with depth down a c. 60 m thick loess section at
267 KAR, Tajikistan. Based on previous (Forster & Heller, 1994) and our own magnetic
268 susceptibility measurements, we correlated the sampled part of the KAR profile to marine
269 oxygen isotope stages (MIS) 19-9 (c. 800–300 ka, Figure S7; Lisiecki & Raymo, 2005). This
270 correlation places the samples from this section beyond the limits of quartz optically
271 stimulated luminescence (OSL) dating. Hence, we estimated the minimum absorbed dose
272 (natural burial dose) received by the uppermost sample to c. 1000 Gy using the post-infrared
273 infrared stimulated luminescence protocol (Table S; Buylaert et al., 2012) on polymineral
274 fine-grains (Figure S8). Assuming a dose rate of 3-4 Gy/ka, which is typical for loess, all
275 samples below the uppermost sample would have received ionising radiation corresponding
276 to an absorbed dose of c. 1000 to 3000 Gy down the profile. The measurement of natural E_1'
277 and HT- E_1' intensity with depth at KAR shows no discerning patterns of incremental
278 increase or decrease (Figure 3b). Whilst, laboratory γ -irradiation experiments on the E_1'
279 signal shows minor variations in the lower dose range (0-2000 Gy; wherein the E_1' intensity
280 first decreases and then increases), unlike that at higher doses (>2000 Gy; Figure 3a). This
281 raises an interesting observation regarding the response of E_1' signal to naturally absorbed
282 doses down KAR, which are also likely to vary between c.1000-3000 Gy down the sequence.
283 In Figure 3a, we observe that E_1' intensity in the lower dose range varies by 5-20% of the
284 natural E_1' values for the representative samples, whereas the variation in E_1' values with
285 depth (and absorbed dose) between loess and soil horizons at KAR ranges by c. 30-50% of
286 the average E_1' values (Figure 3b). Here we note that the average E_1' value is biased by the
287 number of samples taken from the loess versus the soil horizons at KAR, hence the percent
288 variation (if any) in E_1' signature at KAR is likely to be higher than suggested. This implies
289 that the change in E_1' value at KAR is not an artefact of ionising radiation received during
290 burial, but rather represents a change in source (see section 3.2).

291

292

293 **3.2 Applications in aeolian environments: Examples from Central Asia**

294 The ultimate aim of sedimentary provenance analysis in aeolian environments is to identify
295 whether parent rocks or sedimentary sources can be linked to the loess or desert deposits in
296 question, and additionally to determine the trajectory of dust transport pathways and by

297 extension, the most likely climate circulation patterns prevailing at the time of transport and
298 deposition. Our study provides a critical step towards achieving the aim of identifying
299 provenance within sediments by establishing a simplified protocol exploiting characteristic
300 signatures based on defect centres in quartz.

301 Our suite of 114 samples forms two distinct spectral clusters depending on geographic region
302 (Figure 2a). Of the two natural ESR signals measured, the natural E_1' intensity yields the
303 greatest difference between the two regions (Figure 2a). The more diffused peroxy signatures
304 are a result of inherently weak peroxy signal in our samples, and may also reflect the
305 hypothesis that 'peroxy' signals, as measured, represent the overlap of a peroxy radical ($\equiv Si-$
306 $O-O\cdot$, POR) and non-bridging oxygen hole centre ($\equiv Si-O\cdot$, NBOHC) (based on observations
307 by Salh, 2011; Skuja et al., 2020; Figure S9). Nevertheless, the peroxy signals from the two
308 regions are statistically distinguishable, and along with the natural E_1' intensity, can be used
309 as provenance indicators.

310 We observe higher natural E_1' and peroxy signals in the Kazakh loess than the Tajik samples.
311 Since the E_1' and peroxy centres are known to accumulate with time (Odom and Rink, 1989),
312 this suggests that the Kazakh quartz is sourced from older rocks than the Tajik quartz. The
313 suggestion that the Kazakh source rock is older is consistent with the rocks of the central Tien
314 Shan, which are of Palaeozoic age or older (Tursungaziev & Petrov, 2008), and represent the
315 likely source material to the Kazakh loess piedmont (Li et al., 2018; Fitzsimmons et al.,
316 2020). These are older than the predominantly Mesozoic and younger rocks of the Gissar
317 Mountains and northwestern Pamirs (Vlasov et al., 1991), which provide the most likely
318 source rocks for the Tajik loess (Li et al., 2019). The formation of two separate clusters for
319 two independently sourced regions of different source rock age provides support for our
320 proposed approach as a provenance tool.

321 In addition to differentiating likely source regions for different loess sites, we ultimately aim
322 to identify potential changes in source through time down long sedimentary (including loess)
323 sequences such as those found in inland Asia. Figure 4a shows down-profile variations in
324 natural E_1' intensity of loessic quartz at KAR in Tajikistan, a site which preserves multiple
325 primary loess and buried soil (paleosol) horizons (refer SI for details). We observe a marked
326 difference in the natural E_1' and peroxy signature in loess versus paleosol horizons (Figure
327 4b). Recent work using trace element concentrations of loess in Tajikistan, combined with

328 meteorological reanalysis, suggests that provenance is site-dependent and likely to be
 329 dominated by proximal montane sites (Li et al., 2016), with some contribution from distal
 330 sources such as the Karakum desert (Li et al., 2019). The relative contributions of distal and
 331 proximal sources to loess deposits in Tajikistan may have changed over glacial-interglacial
 332 timescales as a result of changes in the dynamics and intensity of atmospheric circulation. We
 333 suggest that our observed changes in paired E_1' -peroxy characteristics represent variability in
 334 the dominant source signature of quartz between the primary (glacial) loess and palaeosol
 335 (interglacial) horizons. At this stage, without more targeted investigations of potential source
 336 rocks, we cannot identify whether the change in the dominant source signature through time
 337 at KAR is a result of proximal and/ or distal transport of dust. Nevertheless, our observations
 338 hold promise for more focused investigations of source signature based on our provenance
 339 method.

340

341

342 **Figure 4. (a)** Down-profile variability in E_1' intensity of fine-grained quartz at KAR,
 343 Tajikistan. The magnetic susceptibility data was measured in the field (refer SI) while LR04
 344 benthic $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ data was obtained from Lisiecki and Raymo (2005); **(b)** Natural E_1' and peroxy
 345 variation in samples from various stratigraphic sections (identified here as loess, palaeosol,
 346 and weakly developed palaeosols) at KAR based on field stratigraphic description and
 347 magnetic susceptibility data.

348

349 **4. Conclusion**

350 We propose a new method for determining the provenance of sedimentary quartz based on
351 the natural accumulation of E_1' and peroxy centres. We confirm, based on empirical
352 measurements of 114 fine-grained loessic quartz samples, that firstly, the natural E_1' and
353 peroxy signals are positively correlated and are likely to arise from Frenkel defect pairs.
354 Secondly, the increase in intensity of these centres with age of the source rock can be seen in
355 the higher values obtained from the Kazakh samples, which are derived from older rocks than
356 the Tajik loess. Therefore, quartz from the Ili basin of SE Kazakhstan yields signals distinct
357 from quartz in the Tajik basin in Tajikistan, indicating a difference in provenance consistent
358 with previously published studies. Furthermore, down-profile measurements at the KAR site
359 in Tajikistan indicates a shift in source between primary loess and paleosol horizons, most
360 likely in response to changes in atmospheric circulation associated with climatic oscillations.
361 Thus, our observations suggest this to be a robust new technique for sediment provenance,
362 that can be applicable to a range of settings, exploiting the characteristics of one of the most
363 ubiquitous minerals found in nature: quartz.

364

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376

377 **Open Research**

378 The authors have currently made the data available as supporting information material and
379 are in the process of archiving their dataset in the open access data repository ‘Mendeley’
380 with the reserved doi: 10.17632/n4fhvswczf.1.

381

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Figure 1.

Figure 2.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.

a**i) A0016 (Kazakhstan)**

Figure 4.

Stratigraphy Legend

- Primary loess
- Weakly developed palaeosol
- Palaeosol
- Clay rich palaeosol unit
- Carbonate enrichment
- Carbonate nodules
- Caliche
- Mn concretions

A novel proxy for tracking the provenance of dust based on paired E_1' -peroxy paramagnetic defect centres in fine-grained quartz

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Table S1

Introduction

The supplementary information of this paper contains three main texts

- (i) Text S1 gives a detailed account of the sampling methodology, geomorphic setting, the stratigraphy and chronology of the sites.
- (ii) Text S2 presents the sample preparation, measurement parameters and protocols and instrumentation.
- (iii) Text S3 is an extended description of the experiments conducted in this study. The results of these experiments are discussed in the main paper.

Text S1. Sampling, Stratigraphy and Chronology

We sampled a total of 114 sediment samples from five loess sections located in southeast (SE) Kazakhstan and the Tajik depression in Tajikistan. Of these, four loess sections (PAN-Panfilov, ASH-Ashubulak, TAU-Taugaraturyuk, and MAL-Malubai) are located along a c. 200 km east-west transect in the piedmonts of

the Zalisky Alatau in the Ili basin of SE Kazakhstan. One loess section, Karamaidan (KAR), is located in the northern margins of the Tajik depression in Tajikistan (Figure 1).

All samples were collected from vertically exposed loess sections, that were cleaned back by at least 1-1.5 m to prevent contamination by recent sediment movement. Samples for electron spin resonance (ESR) measurements were collected in a manner similar to that employed for luminescence dating, i.e., by hammering opaque steel tubes (10 cm-long, 3.5 cm-wide) into freshly cleaned loess sections. Samples at each of the Kazakh sites were sampled down-profile, every c. 0.3 to 0.5 m. A total of 59 samples were collected from four sites in the Ili basin of Kazakhstan, of which 10 samples were taken from PAN, 10 from ASH, 16 from TAU and 23 from MAL (16 samples from profile MAL-A and 7 samples from profile MAL-B). While a total of 55 samples were collected sequentially every c. 0.5 to 1 m from a c. 60 m thick loess section at KAR in Tajikistan.

(a) Ili basin, SE Kazakhstan

The sites in SE Kazakhstan can be seen in Figure S1 and a brief summary of the different sites is given below.

Panfilov (PAN, 43° 22.295' N, 77° 07.670' E; 710 m a.s.l.) is located c. 40 km northeast of Almaty. It is a 5 m-thick loess section that overlies an c. 2 m-thick gravel bed.

Ashubulak (ASH, 43° 28.671' N, 77° 47.379' E; 760 m a.s.l.) is 5 m-thick loess section located ~50 km east of the PAN section. Both PAN and ASH sections are composed almost entirely of pale yellowish primary loess material and do not show any major soil bearing units, apart from the top c. 30 cm of disturbed modern soil.

Taukaraturyk (TAU, 43° 29.445' N, 78° 01.509' E; 769 m a.s.l.) is a 7.5 m-thick loess section located c. 20 km east of ASH. The upper c.30 cm is composed of humic soil unit with modern rootlets and insect holes. The rest of the section is composed of yellowish-beige primary loess with episodic occurrence of angular gravels (1-2 mm), occurring at depth of 1.5–2.0, 2.4–2.8 and 3.8–4.9 m. The occurrence of episodic coarse-grained material in the profile is most likely due to colluvial input from the nearby range front.

Malubai (MAL, 43° 26.312' N, 78° 19.763' E; 815 m a.s.l.) is located c. 25 km east of TAU. The loess section at MAL is composed of two profiles – A and B. Profile A is c. 6 m-thick loess section composed of pale yellowish primary loess, with the presence of an angular gravel layer (c. 0.5–2 cm in diameter) between depths 1.1–1.3 m. Profile B is located c. 6 m north of the main outcrop, Profile A. Profile B consists of two parallel, c. 2 and 1.5 m-thick sections, composed of primary loess, with a c. 2 cm thin layer made of angular gravels (c. 0.5–2 cm in diameter) with silty matrix at 0.40–0.45 m and an imbricated, angular cobble bed at c. 0.9–1.3 m. Both MAL and TAU are located closer to the range front and this may explain episodic sedimentation of colluvial material within their respective profile. This is not the case at sites PAN and ASH, which are located along the peripheral edge of the piedmont loess deposits where these pinch out onto the Ili River floodplain.

Chronology - The chronology of the Kazakh sites was previously presented in Dave et al (2021). The site of PAN, ASH and the top 1m at TAU is luminescence dated to the mid-Holocene (c. 5-17 ka). The quartz as well as feldspar from the site of MAL and remaining site of TAU is close to saturation and hence, the minimum ages at these sites suggest ages of >180 ka (beyond the late Pleistocene).

(b) Tajik depression, Tajikistan

The loess site of Karamaidan (KAR) is located c. 45 km east of the capital city of Dushanbe in Tajikistan. The site has been previously described and dated by palaeomagnetism, and it preserves a continuous record of climate change over the past 1 Ma (Forster & Heller, 1994). The exact exposures at Karamaidan studied by Forster and Heller (1994) are no longer recognisable, therefore, during the 2018 fieldwork in Tajikistan, three new stratigraphically overlapping sections (total c. 130 m thick) were opened and cleaned. We independently constrained the continuity and overlap of these three sections by measuring the in situ magnetic susceptibility with portable Bartington MS3/MS2K magnetic susceptibility (MS) measuring equipment. Our MS composite log closely resembles the Karamaidan profile presented in Forster and Heller (1994) and spans the past >800 ka (see Figure S7).

The KAR (38° 34' 33.47" N, 69° 16' 40.79" E, 1629 m a.s.l.) section investigated in this study begins at 19.6 m and continues down to the depth of 75 m. This section comprises 6 palaeosol and 5 loess units with 3 observed intercalating weak to moderately developed soil units. Visibly distinct dark reddish-brown, clayey palaeosol units were observed between depths 19.6–22.4 m, 27.9–30.1 m, 39.3–44.7 m, 45.3–48.4 m, 62.5–65.3 m, and 70.6–75 m. In the palaeosol unit at depth 62.5–65.3 m, the clay rich horizon overlies a carbonate-enriched layer consisting of nodules (up to 10 cm in diameter) between 64.3–64.3 m followed by a caliche horizon up to 65.3 m. Alternately-occurring pale yellowish-beige primary loess units, with minor carbonate mottling occurs at depths 22.4–25.4 m, 30.1–39.3 m, 44.7–45.3 m, 48.4–62.5 m and 65.3–70.6 m. Intercalating weakly developed soil units within the loess were observed at c. 25.4–25.9 m, c. 55–59 m and c. 68.4–69.6 m.

Chronology - Relative chronology based on correlation of magnetic susceptibility at KAR with that obtained by Forster and Heller (1994) and the global benthic record: Magnetic susceptibility (MS) measurements at the site KAR in Tajikistan were carried out using a portable Bartington Magnetic Susceptibility (MS) system. The Bartington MS system utilises a MS3 meter combined with a MS2K field sensor (a high stability surface scanning sensor) for continuous down-profile measurement of the cleaned outcrop. This system allows for the measurement of volume magnetic susceptibility expressed in SI units as a dimensionless value. Each measurement down-profile was performed on a freshly cleaned, relatively smooth and flat surface, and was individually calibrated with air-temperature to compensate for temperature-induced drift. The measurements were taken continuously every 5 cm for the entire depth of c. 60 m. The resulting volume magnetic susceptibility dataset was correlated by visual comparison to the global benthic $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ curve (Lisiecki & Raymo, 2005) using the magnetostratigraphic constraints of Forster and Heller (1994), ascribing paleosols and loess intervals to global glacial and interglacial stages (see Figure S7). The correlation of magnetic susceptibility to global benthic records for KAR indicates that the studied section varies in age from MIS 19–9 (800–300 ka, refer Figure 4a of the main text and Figure S7).

Text S2. Materials and Methods

(a) Sample preparation: Extraction of fine-grained Quartz

114 sediment samples from 4 sites in Kazakhstan and 1 site in Tajikistan were processed under subdued red-light conditions to obtain fine grained (4-11 μ m) quartz (according to standard luminescence dating preparation techniques; Frechen et al, 1996) at the Institute for Geosciences, Johannes Gutenberg University and the Max Planck Institute for Chemistry (MPIC) in Mainz, Germany. The fine-grained samples were prepared by treating the <63 μ m sediment fraction with 10% HCl followed by 10% H₂O₂ to remove carbonates and organics respectively. The sediment was then treated with 0.1 N sodium oxalate to remove clays. The samples were rinsed at least three to four times with distilled water between each of the aforementioned steps. The fine-grained (4-11 μ m) fraction was obtained from the chemically-treated bulk fraction (<63 μ m) by settling using Stokes law. The separated 4-11 μ m fraction was treated with 37% hexafluorosilicic acid (H₂SiF₆) for 7 days and consequently washed with 10% HCl (to remove fluoride precipitates) to obtain fine grain (4-11 μ m) quartz rich fraction. The etching of the fine grained polymineral fraction was performed at the Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology at Leipzig, Germany.

(b) Electron Spin Resonance: Instrumentation and Methodology

ESR investigations were carried out using an X band Bruker EMX Plus Spectrometer at the Babes Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania. All measurements were made by filling a quartz glass tube with sample at the same volume, with a mass of 100 \pm 4 mg (less than 5% variation) for all samples. Consequently, all ESR measurements were normalised to 100 mg for inter-comparison. In all cases, we measure the peak-to-peak amplitude of the ESR signal to quantify the variation in defect concentration; as the peak-to-peak amplitude variation can be taken as a good approximation of the effective concentration of the defect centres in the sample (Chestnut, 1977). The natural spectra and the measured amplitude of the E₁' peroxy and Al-hole centre of a representative sample (A0329) are shown in Figure S10. Exposure of samples to sunlight was restricted to a minimum during measurements. Gamma irradiations were performed at room temperature at the Centre for Nuclear Technologies, Technical University of Denmark (DTU NUTECH) using a calibrated ⁶⁰Co-60 gamma cell, with a dose rate of about 2 Gy/s (dose rate to water) at the time of irradiation. Dose rate to quartz was estimated to be 0.941 (with relative uncertainty of 2.2%) of dose rate to water based on Monte Carlo simulation considering the irradiation geometry used. All ESR measurements on gamma irradiated quartz were carried out after waiting for more than 2 weeks after irradiation.

Three types of defect centres were investigated in this study – E₁', Peroxy and Al-hole centre. Intensity of E₁' and peroxy defect centre was measured for all samples while Al-hole signal was quantified only for selected samples. E₁' was recorded at room temperature at a modulation amplitude of 0.05 mT, centerfield of 0.3365 T, conversion time of 75.13 ms and a microwave power of 0.02 mW. Each data point for E₁' is an average of 3 repeat measurements on the same aliquot, wherein each repeat measurement is an average of 6 scans with a sweep time of 30 s each. The E₁' intensity was determined using the peak-to-peak height of the spectrum centred at g= 2.006 (e.g. Timar-Gabor, 2018). The peroxy defect was measured at room temperature with a modulation amplitude of 0.1 mT, centerfield of 0.3350 T,

conversion time of 40.96 ms and at a microwave power of 10 mW. Each peroxy data point is an average of 3 repeat measurements on the same aliquot, each of which is an average of 3 scans with a sweep time of 120s. The peroxy signature was determined using the peak-to-peak height from $g=2.003$ to $g=2.009$ (Odom & Rink, 1989). The 3 repeat measurements for E_1' and peroxy intensities were performed on three different days over the course of a year for all the samples in this study. The tube was placed at a random angle for every measurement. The measurements performed in this manner assures us of the stability of the measured signal as well as the precision of the instrument.

The ESR intensity of the Al-hole centre was recorded at a temperature of 90 K, with a modulation amplitude of 0.1 mT, centerfield of 0.3350 T, sweep time of 120 s and a microwave power of 2 mW. Each data point for Al-hole centre intensity is an average of 3 scans carried out by rotating the sample by 120 degree between each scan. The signal of Al-hole was quantified using peak-to-peak height from $g=2.018$ to $g=1.993$ (Toyoda & Falguères, 2003).

(c) Optically stimulated luminescence measurements

In this study we used optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) method for two main purposes.

First, to check the purity of quartz measured by ESR. 2-3 aliquots of each quartz sample was tested for possible feldspar contamination by checking the IRSL (infrared stimulation) intensity after a short beta irradiation (c. 19 Gy). Only pure quartz samples (with an absence of an IR signal) were used for ESR measurements.

Second, to evaluate the minimum absorbed dose for samples at the top and bottom of the KAR profile. Correlation of magnetic susceptibility to global benthic records for site KAR suggests that it varies in age from c. 800-300 ka (MIS 19-9; Figure S7). It is well known that natural quartz OSL signal (which relates to the absorbed dose in quartz) saturates between c. 100-300 Gy (Timar-Gabor & Wintle, 2013). Therefore, we investigated the absorbed dose from polymineral fine grains since feldspars in polymineral aliquots are known to saturate at higher doses (Buylaert et al., 2012). We undertook post-Infrared Infrared (pIRIR) stimulated luminescence measurements at high doses (up to 3325 Gy) for two polymineral fine-grained (4-11 μ m) samples from KAR, based on the protocol by Buylaert et al (2012). We evaluated the absorbed dose for the two samples, one from the top (sample A0276, depth=20 m) and the other from the bottom (A0329, depth =72.5 m) of the profile. The polymineral fine grains for these measurements were derived from the same samples as their quartz equivalent. 3 polymineral aliquots each of the samples A0276 and A0329 were evaluated based on the protocol described in Table S1 and the results are summarised in Figure S8. Figure S8 shows that sample A0276 is close to saturation, with a burial dose c. 970 Gy, whilst sample A0329 was completely saturated. This implies that the uppermost sample at site KAR received a minimum absorbed dose of c. 1000 Gy, which increases with depth (assuming age increases with depth) at KAR.

The quartz purity and pIR₅₀IR₂₉₀ measurements were made using an automated Risø TL-DA-20 reader equipped with a ⁹⁰Sr/⁹⁰Y beta sources. The sample was stimulated using IR LED (870 \pm 30 nm, 300 mW/cm²) and blue LED (470 \pm 30 nm, 80 mW/cm²) and the emitted luminescence signal was detected by by EMI 9235QA photomultiplier tube using a combination of Schott BG-39 and BG-3 filters to detect feldspar emissions.

Text S3. Extended description of results

(a) Reproducibility of results from KAR section

Reproducibility of results from the same site, i.e., measurement of E_1' and peroxy signals from multiple samples from the same stratigraphic horizon (a few cm apart) can inform us of the accuracy of our measurements. Here we provide one such example that assures us of the reproducibility of our results. Two samples A0293-A and A0293-B were taken at depths 36.8 m and 37 m respectively from a loess horizon ascribed to stratigraphic level corresponding to the beginning of MIS 12. The fine-grain quartz extracted from these samples exhibit identical values (within <1.5 % of each other) for both, E_1' as well as peroxy measurements.

(b) Experiments on selected samples, A0016 and A0329: Experimental setup and methodology

Two fine-grained (4-11 μ m) quartz samples were selected, one each from Kazakhstan (A0016, TAU) and Tajikistan (A0329, KAR), to investigate the effect of gamma (γ) irradiation and heating on the ESR centres: E_1' , peroxy and Al-hole centres. Sample A0016 and A0329 were divided into 11 subsamples of c.100 mg each and irradiated with given γ -doses: 0 Gy (referred to as the natural sample), 100 Gy, 200 Gy, 500 Gy, 1000 Gy, 2000 Gy, 5000 Gy, 10000 Gy, 20000 Gy and 40000 Gy.

First, all aliquots of the irradiated samples were measured at room temperature to record the corresponding intensity of the E_1' and peroxy centres. The Al-hole measurements were recorded at 90 K for all aliquots. Following this, all the aliquots of sample A0016 and A0329 were heated stepwise at 300 °C, 350 °C, and 400°C for 15 min each and the corresponding intensity of the E_1' and peroxy centres was measured after each heating step. The results of this experiment are summarised in Figure S5 and Figure S6.

(c) Simulation of E_1' , Peroxy and Al-hole signals

Of the three ESR signals investigated in this study, the E_1' signals obtained from our samples are well defined. However, the peroxy and Al-hole centres are comparatively weak. Therefore, in order to assess the behavior of the ESR signals in our samples with expected signal behaviour based on literature, we simulated the signal of all the centres under study with known parameters from literature. The E_1' and peroxy signal was simulated using parameters from Jani et al (1983) and Ikeya (1993), while the simulation of Al-hole centre was based on the Al-hole signal from a natural quartz sample, EVA-1095, combined with parameters from literature (Nuttall & Weil, 1981; Ikeya, 1993). Sample EVA-1095 (125-212 μ m) is a natural quartz sample from Lake Durthong, Australia (Fitzsimmons, 2017) and has a well characterised Al-hole centre, with relatively high concentration (Benzid & Timar-Gabor, 2020). Bruker WinEPR SimFonia software was used to perform the simulation and fitting.

In order to compare the effective apparent concentrations of the Al-hole centres in samples A0016 (Kazakhstan) and A0329 (Tajikistan), we used the 'simulated' Al-hole signal to obtain the effective Al-hole concentration. This was done, since the measurement of Al-hole concentration in natural fine grain quartz, especially a weak signal, is likely to have an interfering component from the peroxy signal, as also

inferred from dating studies by Timar-Gabor et al. (2018). Therefore, the simulated signal was fitted to the measured Al-hole signal from two fine-grained (4-11 μ m) quartz samples, A0016 (Kazakhstan) and A0329 (Tajikistan) with a given γ -dose of 0 Gy (natural sample) and 20000 Gy. These simulated signals were then integrated twice to obtain the effective Al-hole concentration (equal to the area under the curve). The results from simulations of the Al-hole centre and its effective concentration in the samples are summarized in Figure S4. The results from Figure S4 clearly illustrate that the concentration of Al-hole centre in Kazakh samples is higher than the Tajik samples. The simulations of the E_1' and peroxy centre with respect to their natural signals are shown in Figure S9.

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Figure S1. Sites under study in the Ili basin of southeast Kazakhstan (PAN, MAL, TAU and ASH; fieldwork 2017) and the Tajik depression (KAR) in Tajikistan (fieldwork 2018).

Figure S2. Variation in intensity of E_1' centre with γ -irradiation. Here the E_1' intensity is normalised to its natural value for all measurements. The experiments were performed at room temperature on 4-11 μm natural quartz from different geographic locations.

Figure S3. Variation of natural peroxy intensity in fine-grained quartz with γ -irradiation in samples (a) A0016 (Kazakhstan) and (b) A0329 (Tajikistan).

Figure S4. Variation in intensity of Al-hole centre with γ -irradiation for sample (a) A0016 and (b) A0329. Part (i) and (ii) show the difference between intensity of Al-hole centres in natural (0 Gy) and a γ -irradiated aliquot (20000 Gy) based on simulations for samples A0016 and A0329 respectively. All the intensities for Al-hole centre are baseline corrected.

Figure S5. Variation of E_1' intensity in γ -irradiated aliquots for sample (a) A0016 and (b) A00329 with temperature. Plot (c) and (d) show the variation of E_1' intensity with γ -irradiation with subsequent stepwise heating at 300°, 350° and 400°C for sample A0016 (Kazakhstan) and A00329 (Tajikistan) respectively.

Figure S6. Variation of peroxy intensity in γ -irradiated aliquots of sample (a) A0016 and (b) A00329 with temperature. Plot (c) and (d) show the variation of peroxy intensity with γ -irradiation with subsequent stepwise heating at 300°, 350° and 400°C for sample A0016 (Kazakhstan) and A00329 (Tajikistan) respectively.

Figure S7. Correlation between the global benthic curve (Lisiecki and Raymo, 2005) and the magnetic susceptibility measurements obtained at Karamaidan (KAR) by Forster and Heller (1994) and that obtained in this study (fieldwork 2018). The section highlighted in the red dashed-box represents the c. 60 m section investigated in this study and M-B refers to the Matuyama-Bruhnes boundary.

Figure S8. Dose response curve of fine grain polyminerals constructed using $PIR_{50}R_{290}$ protocol (Buylaert et al., 2012) to estimate the burial dose in the samples (a) A0276 (uppermost sample) (b) A0329 (bottom sample) at KAR, Tajikistan.

Figure S9. Comparison of natural and simulated spectra of the E_1' and peroxy centre of sample (a) A0016 (Kazakhstan) and (b) A0329 (Tajikistan). Here POR refers to peroxy radical and NBOHC refers to non-bridging oxygen hole centres.

Figure S10. Spectra of all the defect centres measured in this study (from representative sample A0329).

Table S1. Protocol for $pIR_{50}IR_{290}$ investigations to evaluate the absorbed dose (or equivalent dose) from polymineral fine grain samples (after Buylaert et al., 2012).

<i>pIR₅₀IR₂₉₀ protocol (Buylaert et al, 2012)</i>		
Step	Treatment	Signal measured
1	Dose (Natural or laboratory)	-
2	Preheat 60s at 320 °C	-
3	IRSL, 200s at 50°C	-
4	IRSL, 200s at 290 °C	L_{nr} or L_x
5	Test dose	-
6	Preheat 60s at 320 °C	-
7	IRSL, 200s at 50°C	-
8	IRSL, 200s at 290 °C	T_n or T_x
9	IRSL, 100s at 325 °C	-
10	Return to step 1	-